

THE TEACHING-LEARNING ENVIRONMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN THE CITY DIVISION OF ILAGAN: ITS EFFECT ON THE LEVEL OF MOTIVATION AND PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS AND TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of the teaching-learning environment on the motivation and performance of Senior High School (SHS) teachers and students in the City Division of Ilagan during the 2022-2023 school year. Using a descriptive research design, data were gathered from 209 teachers and 372 students across 15 public SHS schools through questionnaires, informal interviews, and documentary analysis. Findings revealed that both groups had positive perceptions of the teaching-learning environment, with teachers rating support and resources higher, while students favored facilities. Intrinsic motivation was high among both teachers and students, though extrinsic motivation significantly influenced teacher performance. The study concluded that the teaching-learning environment, motivation, and performance are interconnected but vary according to school size, classification, and location. Recommendations include enhancing resources, feedback mechanisms, and monitoring to improve the SHS teaching-learning environment in Ilagan.

Keywords: *Teaching-learning environment, Motivation, Performance, Senior High School, City Division of Ilagan*

INTRODUCTION

Education is not a one-size-fits-all endeavor, rather, it is a complex interplay of various factors that shape the learning experience. Among these factors, the teaching-

learning environment emerges as a crucial element that can significantly influence the motivation and performance of both students and teachers.

The teaching-learning environment encompasses the physical, social, and instructional conditions in which education takes place. It is the overall context in which teachers facilitate learning and students engage in the educational process. The quality of the teaching-learning environment can have a significant impact on the motivation and performance of both students and teachers. A positive, engaging, and supportive environment can enhance student's motivation, learning outcomes, and overall well-being, while a negative or ineffective environment can have the opposite effect. For teachers, it can influence their job satisfaction, teaching effectiveness, and professional development.

Creating an effective teaching-learning environment involves various factors, including facilities, resources, support, environment, and technology. Each of these elements plays a crucial role in influencing the motivation and performance of both teachers and students. A well-designed teaching-learning environment fosters motivation by creating a positive and engaging atmosphere. Adequate resources and support empower teachers to deliver effective instruction, leading to improved student performance. Access to technology can enhance students' interest and engagement in learning, making the educational experience more enjoyable and relevant and positive interpersonal relationships. A supportive environment contributes to a sense of belonging, motivating both teachers and students to excel. Thus, a holistic approach to the teaching-learning environment that considers facilities, resources, support, environment, and technology can create an environment conducive to motivation and high performance for both teachers and students. Continuous efforts to adapt and improve these elements will contribute to the overall success of an educational institution.

In the Philippines, the teaching-learning environment particularly in public secondary education faced various challenges including resource limitations, poor classroom conditions, teacher quality and training, etc. Many schools, especially in remote areas, still face resource limitations such as inadequate classroom facilities, a lack of textbooks and learning materials, and limited access to technology and the Internet. In some areas, classrooms may not meet safety and sanitation standards due to overcrowded which can negatively impact the learning environment.

According to a government survey, many public schools need repair; school buildings need serious renovation or replacement and some schools still lack the needed facilities. Navarro (2022), reveals that there are insufficient classrooms in some schools due to an increased number of enrolments. Moreover, classrooms in other areas do not meet quality and safety standards and deteriorate due to calamities. Regarding water sanitation and hygiene (WASH) facilities, the Philippines lags behind other countries in providing WASH facilities to schools. Concerning electricity access to schools, the Philippines still struggles to complete the electrification of schools. In addition, rates of computer and Internet access in schools are low compared with neighboring countries that have already achieved universal computer and Internet access for their schools.

Brilliantes et.al (2019) likewise found out that the facilities in some schools such as restrooms, clinics, canteen, and laboratories are not available or not functional, if present. Also, the delivery of tools and equipment is not yet complete and there have been instances that the tools or equipment being delivered has incorrect specifications or incorrect delivery of items like incorrect textbooks, laboratory chairs, and tables delivered for regular classrooms. This shows that there are still gaps in the teaching and learning environment of the schools which could affect the motivation and performance of teachers and students, the quality of education, and the overall effectiveness of the education system.

The City of Ilagan, particularly where this study was conducted, also encountered various gaps and challenges in the teaching-learning environment, particularly on inadequacy of school facilities and resources. As a teacher in one of these schools, the researcher personally encountered deficiencies in school facilities, encompassing inadequacies in laboratories, computer rooms, classrooms, and other essential resources which she believes affect the motivation and performance of the teachers and the students and the overall effectiveness of the education system. Consequently, she felt the need to reconcile these problems through communicating the result of the study to the relevant stakeholders to make positive changes in the teaching-learning environment. This situation prompted the researcher to conduct this study to further determine the effect of the teaching-learning environment on teachers and on students' level of motivation and performance with the end goal of enhancing their motivation and performance by improving the teaching-learning environment of the schools.

Conceptual Framework

Given that this study explores the impact of the teaching-learning environment on the motivation and performance of Senior High School (SHS) teachers and students, it draws upon several key concepts related to the educational environment and its influence on both groups. These concepts provide a foundation for understanding how various elements of the teaching-learning environment—such as physical infrastructure, instructional resources, social dynamics, and technological tools—affect the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, as well as the overall performance, of both students and teachers. By examining these factors, the study seeks to uncover how a well-designed, supportive, and resource-rich educational environment can foster higher motivation levels and enhance academic and professional outcomes within the school setting.

The teaching-learning environment, often referred to as the "learning environment" or "educational environment," encompasses the physical, psychological, social, and instructional conditions and factors that influence and shape the teaching and learning process. It is the context in which education takes place and includes various elements and characteristics that can either enhance or hinder the effectiveness of education. This environment impacts both teachers and students and plays a significant role in determining the quality of education. Havidz and Mujakiah (2023) define the term as the premise and all facilities for daily learning activities. The learning environment is part of the learning process to achieve learning objectives, and the environment affects the

teaching and learning activities of the school. The learning environment is the environment, both physical and social, that affects the learning process.

According to Balog (2018), the learning environment comprises some components that influence the student's learning curve including people; teaching materials, technical tools, and learning resources; curriculum, training, and instruction, and physical environment/learning space. The people are the individuals that affect the student directly or indirectly through connection or relationship which can contribute to students' growth and success in their career aspect. The teaching materials, technical tools, and learning resources are the teaching materials, highly advanced tools, or other instructional resources that are aligned with the curriculum as a part of student learning support. The curriculum, training, and instruction are the core foundations of the learning process; they influence one another and play vital roles in facilitating the flow of knowledge and delivery of instructional content/curriculum. The physical environment/learning space refers to the physical setting of the learner's environment which should evoke positive responses and hold the interests of those who inhabit it. In addition to this, technology was also found as one component of the teaching and learning environment that increases student motivation and joy of learning if used in the classroom (Wieking, 2016).

Based on the components given by Balog, the researcher identified key components that play a significant role in influencing the motivation and performance of both teachers and students. These components include facilities, support, environment, resources, and technology.

Facilities encompass various aspects such as classrooms, laboratories, and libraries, essential for educational activities. Well-designed and equipped classrooms contribute to a positive learning environment, with comfortable seating, proper lighting, and effective use of space. Access to specialized spaces like laboratories and a well-organized library enhances the overall quality of education.

Support is another crucial component, involving assistance, resources, and services provided to teachers and students. Adequate administrative support, efficient logistics, and communication systems enable teachers to focus on teaching, leading to improved student performance. Training and professional development opportunities for teachers also contribute to their motivation and ability to provide high-quality education.

The environment, as a component, influences motivation by fostering diversity and inclusivity. A diverse and inclusive environment creates a sense of belonging, positively impacting the motivation and performance of both teachers and students.

Resources, including up-to-date textbooks and supplementary materials, are essential for effective teaching and learning. The availability and effective use of classroom resources contribute to a dynamic and engaging educational experience, positively influencing motivation and performance.

Lastly, technology plays a pivotal role in the digital age. Its effective integration into educational practices enhances engagement, facilitates interactive learning, and broadens access to information. The proper use of technology positively impacts the motivation and performance of both teachers and students in the educational process.

Indeed, a well-designed teaching-learning environment with adequate facilities, resources, support, a positive atmosphere, and appropriate technology can contribute to the motivation and performance of both teachers and students. When these elements are effectively combined, they create a dynamic and inspiring educational setting that positively influences the motivation and performance of both teachers and students.

Figure 1. The Input-Process-Output Model of the Study

With the end goal of determining the effect of the teaching and learning environment on teachers' and students' levels of motivation and performance, this study was guided by the research paradigm.

The input frame of the study consists of the profile of the school which includes school size, classification, and location. These data formed part of the study for it has a great impact on the teaching and learning environment. The data on the perceptions of the respondents on the teaching and learning environment of the SHS in terms of facilities, environment, support, resources, and technology also formed part of this study for the researcher to assess the schools' teaching and learning environment. The core of the study is the data gathered on the perceived level of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation as well as the performance of the respondents.

The process indicates the steps and employment of statistical tools to analyze and interpret the data gathered. The output of this study indicates the main purpose of this study which is the enhancement of students' and teachers' motivation and performance which the researcher believes can help to further improve the quality of education, particularly in the Senior High School.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effect of the learning environment on Senior High School teachers' and students' level of motivation and performance in the City Division of Ilagan for the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the SHS in the City of Ilagan in terms of:
 - a. School Size
 - b. School Classification
 - c. School Location
2. How do the respondents perceive the teaching and learning environment of the SHS in terms of:
 - a. Facilities
 - b. Environment
 - c. Support
 - d. Resources
 - e. Technology
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the two groups of respondents on the teaching-learning environment in terms of:
 - a. Facilities
 - b. Environment
 - c. Support
 - d. Resources
 - e. Technology
4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents when grouped according to profile?

5. What is the level of teaching and learning motivation of teachers and students in terms of:
 - a. intrinsic
 - b. extrinsic
 6. Is there a significant difference in the level of motivation of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. intrinsic
 - b. extrinsic
 7. Is there a significant difference in the level of motivation of the respondents when grouped according to profile?
 8. What is the performance of the students and teachers?
 9. Is there a significant relationship between and among the perceived teaching and learning environment, level of motivation, and performance of the respondents?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive method of research in completing the study. According to Calderon and Gonzales (1993), this method of research is proper for a fact-finding study with adequate and accurate interpretation of the findings. It describes with emphasis what exists such as conditions, practices, situations, or any phenomena.

This method is considered appropriate for this study since it aims to describe the effect of the teaching-learning environment on SHS teachers' and students' levels of motivation and performance.

Research Locale

The research was conducted in public schools offering the SHS Program in the City Division of Ilagan. The schools coming from urban areas include Isabela National High School and Isabela School of Arts and Trades. The schools coming from rural areas include Sta. Isabel National High School, Isabela School of Arts and Trades-Annex, Gayong-Gayong Integrated School, Rang-Ayan National High School, San Lorenzo Integrated School, Managing Integrated School, Lupigue Integrated School, San Rafael National High, San Antonio National Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School, Dappat Integrated School, Ilagan West National High School, Sindun Bayabo Integrated School and San Pedro Integrated School.

Selection and Description of the Respondents

The respondents of this study were the public teachers and students of the 15 schools implementing the SHS Program in the City Division of Ilagan for the school year 2022-2023. The teacher respondents include full-time and part-time SHS teachers

teaching grades 11 and 12 students. The student respondents were the selected grades 11 and 12 students enrolled at public SHS in the City Division of Ilagan. The student respondents were selected using Slovin's formula. For the students to have an equal chance of becoming respondents, the researcher divided the sample into two meanings, 50% grade 11 and 50% grade 12. Then draw lots were done. Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents by school.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

School	Teachers	Students	
		Enrolment	Sample
1. Isabela National High School	65	2500	172
2. Isabela School of Arts and Trade- Main	44	1100	76
3. Rang-Ayan National High School	10	323	22
4. Sta. Isabel National High School	11	206	14
5. San Rafael National Vocational High School	7	178	12
6. San Antonio National Agro- Industrial and Vocational High School	7	186	13
7. Ilagan West National High School	8	117	8
8. ISAT Cabannungan Annex	6	112	8
9. Manaring Integrated School	8	165	11
10. San Lorenzo Integrated School	9	172	12
11. Lupigue Integrated School	7	86	6
12. Dappat Integrated School	7	94	7
13. Gayong-Gayong Integrated School	7	78	5
14. Sindun Bayabo Integrated School	6	48	3
15. San Pedro Integrated School	7	45	3
TOTAL	209	5410	372

Data Gathering Instruments

The following tools were used to gather the needed data for the study.

Questionnaire. The questionnaire was the main data-gathering instrument. It is a researcher-made questionnaire that was validated through pilot testing. It is divided into three parts. The first part of the questionnaire deals with the school profile which includes school size, classification, and location. The second part is composed of statements that assess the perceptions of the respondents on the school teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, resources, technology, environment, and support. The last part is composed of statements that determine the respondents' level of teaching and learning motivation.

Informal Interview. This was also conducted by the researcher to validate the responses of the respondents in the questionnaire. This method assisted the respondents by clarifying some ambiguous parts that may defeat the real purpose of the study.

Documentary Analysis. This was used by the researcher to gather the data on the school profile, the general average of the students which was taken from their form 138 (Learner's Report Card), and the performance of the teachers which was taken from their IPCRF rating for the school year 2022-2023.

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure that valid data were gathered in the conduct of the study, the researcher followed sets of procedures, and observing protocols, especially in floating the questionnaire.

The researcher sought the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of this study. The approval of the superintendent served as the passport of the researcher in gathering pertinent data by administering the questionnaire to the respondents in the different schools implementing the Senior High School Program in the City Division of Ilagan. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire through a scheduled meeting with the respondents.

The questionnaires were retrieved immediately after the respondents have answered completely and accurately the needed data. Data were tabulated and analyzed to realize the purpose of this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Profile of Schools

a. School Size

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Schools in Terms of School Size

School Size	Population	Frequency	Percentage
Small	Less than 440	13	86.67
Medium	441-840	0	0
Large	841-1,240	1	6.67
Very Large	1,240 and above	1	6.67
Total		15	100

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of schools in terms of school size. The majority of the schools, 13 or 86.67 percent have enrolment populations of less than 440. These include Rang-Ayan National High School, Sta. Isabel National High School, San Rafael National Vocational High School, San Antonio National Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School, Ilagan West National High School, ISAT Cabannungan Annex, Manaring Integrated School, San Lorenzo Integrated School, Lupigue Integrated School, Dappat Integrated School, Gayong-Gayong Integrated School, Sindun Bayabo Integrated School, and San Pedro Integrated School; one or 6.67 percent has a population of 841- 1,240 which is Isabela School of Arts and Trade- Main, and another one or 6.67 percent is in the bracket of 1,240 and above enrolment population namely, Isabela National High School.

The data implies that most of the school respondents in the City Division of Ilagan belong to small-sized of population based on the classification set as per DepEd Order no. 19 series of 2016 where schools with a population of less than 440 are considered small schools, those with a 441-840 enrolment population are considered medium schools, those with an 841-1240 population are categorized as large schools and those with a 1,240 and above population are categorized as a very large schools.

b. School Classification

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Schools in Terms of School Classification

School Classification	Frequency	Percentage
National	6	40
Integrated	9	60

Stand- Alone	0	0
Total	15	100

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of schools in terms of school classification. Of the 15 respondent schools, there are nine or 60 percent are classified 'Integrated' including Manaring Integrated School, San Lorenzo Integrated School, Lupigue Integrated School, Dappat Integrated School, San Pedro Integrated School, Isabela School of Arts and Trade- Main, ISAT Cabannungan Annex, Gayong-Gayong Integrated School, and Sindun Bayabo Integrated School; while six or 45 percent belong to the 'National' school classification, namely, Isabela National High School, Rang-Ayan National High School, Sta. Isabel National High School, San Rafael National Vocational High School, San Antonio National Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School, and Ilagan West National High School.

Data reveals that the majority of the schools in the City of Ilagan are under the Integrated school classification. This further means that the schools offering the SHS Program also offer kindergarten, elementary, and junior high school and share the same school head and other resources.

The said finding was supported by a substitute bill entitled "An Act Ensuring Access to Free Secondary Education by Converting the Public Elementary Schools into Integrated Schools" which seeks to ensure access of elementary graduates to quality public high school education through the establishment of integrated schools providing complete basic education. This act could be the main reason why a majority of SHS schools in the City of Ilagan belong to the Integrated School Classification.

c. School Location

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Schools in Terms of School Location

School Location	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	2	13.33
Rural	13	86.67
Total	15	100

Table 4 reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of schools in terms of school location. There 13 or 86.67 percent of schools are located in rural areas including Manaring Integrated School, San Lorenzo Integrated School, Lupigue Integrated School, Dappat Integrated School, San Pedro Integrated School, ISAT Cabannungan Annex, Gayong-Gayong Integrated School, Sindun Bayabo Integrated School, Rang-Ayan National High School, Sta. Isabel National High School, San Rafael National Vocational High School, San Antonio National Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School, and Ilagan West National High School; while only 2 or 13.33 percent are located in urban areas namely, Isabela National High School and Isabela School of Arts and Trade.

It can be seen in the table that the majority of the school respondents are in rural areas. This is because of the effort of the government to make education accessible to all, especially to the rural communities to reduce the number of out-of-school youths in the country through “The Integrated Public Schools Act of 2016” which seeks to ensure access to elementary graduates to quality public high school education through the establishment of integrated schools providing complete basic education. According to Rep. Vilma Santos-Recto, the creation of integrated schools will allow elementary graduates, especially from rural communities, to continue their education at a lesser cost, especially on travel expenditures. This will also result in savings for the government as facilities of existing elementary schools may be utilized for the use of incoming high school students with only repairs and a few additional classrooms to be constructed, rather than constructing a separate high school in the area.

The Teaching and Learning Environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as perceived by the respondents

a. Facilities

Table 5. The Teaching and Learning Environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Facilities

Facilities	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The school has available classrooms/Laboratories/Shops and other learning facilities.	3.09	Agree	3.16	Agree
2. Classrooms are equipped with electric fans.	3.45	Strongly Agree	3.28	Strongly Agree
3. The school has TVL and non-TVL tools and equipment.	2.89	Agree	3.16	Agree
4. The school has adequate water, health and sanitation facilities	3.30	Strongly Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
5. The school has a functional library.	2.79	Agree	3.21	Agree
6. The school has a functional clinic.	3.32	Strongly Agree	3.38	Strongly Agree
7. The school has a sports facility with required equipment.	2.62	Agree	3.10	Agree
8. The classroom has enough seats and desks for every student.	3.21	Agree	3.15	Agree
9. The school has available buildable space for the construction of SHS buildings.	3.16	Agree	3.15	Agree
10. Gender Sensitive comfort rooms are available.	3.08	Agree	2.99	Agree
11. A school- managed canteen is operational.	3.19	Agree	3.22	Agree

12. The school has safe facilities in place to address hazard threats (e.g. fire exits, fire extinguishers, appropriate electrical wirings).	3.38	Strongly Agree	3.34	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.12	Agree	3.20	Agree

Table 5 provides data on the teaching and learning environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as perceived by the respondents in terms of facilities.

As gleaned from the table, the teacher and student respondents presented the same level of assessment on the teaching-learning environment of the Senior High Schools in terms of facilities. The two groups of respondents rated it 'Agree' with an average mean of 3.12 and 3.20 respectively.

The items on the availability of classrooms/Laboratories/Shops, TVL and Non-TVL tools and equipment, functional library, sports facility with the required equipment, seats and desks for every student, buildable space for the construction of SHS buildings, gender sensitive comfort rooms, and the canteen was rated by both teacher and student respondents 'Agree'; while the availability of classrooms with equipped electric fans, water, health and sanitation facilities, functional clinic and safe facilities in place to address hazard threats (e.g. fire exits, fire extinguishers, appropriate electrical wirings) have been rated 'Strongly Agree'.

It is also noted that items on availability of sports facility with required equipment have been rated at the lowest mean by the teachers and availability of Gender Sensitive comfort rooms by the students. This means that there are schools that still lack the required facilities which is believed to be a crucial component of a conducive teaching and learning environment.

The cited finding is supported by Ganaden et. al (2017) who averred that public schools face diverse problems that hinder the delivery of quality education and some of these are inadequacy of facilities like sports facilities that cause students 'reluctance to sports participation.

Furthermore, as revealed in the interview with some students who belong to the third gender or "non-binary" they feel excluded or uncomfortable using restrooms that are designated for a specific gender. This discomfort can then contribute to a negative school experience and may even impact a student's overall well-being. This is contrary to the provision of DepEd Order no. 32, s. 2017 where schools should ensure that all facilities are safe, functional, adequate, sanitary, gender and culture-sensitive, and accessible to persons with Disabilities (PWDs).

b. Environment

Table 6. The Teaching and Learning Environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Environment

Environment	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Classrooms have sufficient space and have the convenience for teachers and students to move and work.	3.33	Strongly Agree	3.13	Agree
2. Classrooms have convenient seating arrangements suitable for activity-based learning.	3.37	Strongly Agree	3.18	Agree
3. Classrooms have sufficient light and ventilation.	3.42	Strongly Agree	3.11	Agree
4. The school ensures a teaching learning environment that promotes individual and team health and well-being.	3.56	Strongly Agree	3.25	Strongly Agree
5. The school implements policies and procedures for safe, secure and equitable learning environment.	3.63	Strongly Agree	3.32	Strongly Agree
6. The school promotes inclusive learning environment.	3.63	Strongly Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
7. The school ensures efficient management of physical and IT- enabled learning structures.	3.44	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree
8. The school ensures a learning environment that fosters health and well- being of learners and school personnel.	3.55	Strongly Agree	3.16	Agree
9. The school establishes a mechanism for a	3.55	Strongly Agree	3.16	Agree

resilient learning environment.				
10. The school ensures a learning environment that fosters positive discipline.	3.61	Strongly Agree	3.20	Agree
11. The teachers have their own lounge and/or work area.	3.28	Strongly Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
12. The school practices proper waste disposal.	3.35	Strongly Agree	3.08	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.48	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree

Table 6 presents data on the teaching and learning environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as perceived by the respondents in terms of environment.

As shown in the table, the teacher and student respondents differ in their perceptions in terms of environment. The teacher respondents rated it ‘Strongly Agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.48; while the student respondents rated it ‘Agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.19.

The results indicate that the teacher respondents have a better perception of the teaching-learning in terms of environment compared to the student respondents. Teachers may have highly positive perceptions of their learning environment because they have years of experience in education, which can provide them with a broader perspective on the challenges and successes in the classroom while students’ experience is more limited, and they may not have the same long-term view of the educational process. Moreover, teachers are more aware of the different policies and guidelines set by the Department of Education regarding the teaching and learning environment including classroom size requirements under DO 64, S. 2017 also known as “Establishing the Minimum Performance Standards and Specifications (MPSS) for DepEd School Buildings” that guide the Department and other stakeholders in the preparation of plans— architectural, structural, electrical, fire protection and sanitary— to ensure the comfort and safety of the occupants of the school buildings.

c. Support

Table 7. The Teaching and Learning Environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Support

Support	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The school has an allotment of SHS MOOE and capital outlay.	3.51	Strongly Agree	3.08	Agree
2. The school has non-teaching staff	3.11	Agree	3.19	Agree
a. Registrar	3.13	Agree	3.16	Agree
b. SHS Administrative Assistant	3.52	Strongly Agree	3.24	Agree
c. Librarian	2.47	Disagree	3.08	Agree
d. SHS Guidance counselor	2.92	Agree	3.27	Strongly Agree
e. ICT Coordinator	3.65	Strongly Agree	3.20	Agree
3. There are enough teachers to teach the SHS students with a ratio of 40:1.	3.00	Agree	3.07	Agree
4. Technical assistance is provided to teachers.	3.49	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree
5. Classroom observation is regularly conducted.	3.72	Strongly Agree	3.17	Agree
6. There is a provision of school supplies to teachers.	3.39	Strongly Agree	3.17	Agree
7. All teachers are trained on the core learning areas and specialized subjects.	3.37	Strongly Agree	3.27	Strongly Agree
8. Teachers are regularly trained in new and effective teaching-learning strategies.	3.39	Strongly Agree	3.22	Agree
9. The school has available industry, office, and agency partners as work immersion venues.	3.64	Strongly Agree	3.24	Agree
10. The school has available funds for the	3.03	Agree	3.12	Agree

insurance of the SHS learners.				
11. The school has a Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) whose elected leaders meet regularly.	3.62	Strongly Agree	3.26	Strongly Agree
12. The school has organized and capacitated the School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Committee (SDRRMC)	3.55	Strongly Agree	3.24	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.34	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree

Table 7 reflects the teaching and learning environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as perceived by the respondents in terms of Support.

The table shows that the teacher respondents assessed the teaching and learning environment of the Senior High Schools in terms of Support to 'Strongly Agree' on a mean of 3.34 and 3.19 or 'Agree' by the students, respectively. This means that teacher and student respondents perceived differently the teaching-learning environment in terms of support. The teachers have a better perception of the teaching-learning environment in terms of support except for the availability of non-teaching staff, particularly the librarian and guidance counselor. Teachers are more aware that there are indeed no available librarians and guidance counselors in their school compared to students. This is perhaps the reason why their perception rating on the availability of non-teaching staff is lower.

Moreover, the items availability of non-teaching staff particularly librarians, and adequacy of teachers to teach the SHS students with a ratio of 40:1 obtained the lowest weighted means for both teacher and student respondents. The findings indicate that not all schools in the City Division of Ilagan have non-teaching staff which is contrary to the provision of DepEd Order no. 19 s. 2016 where Senior High Schools should have the required staffing pattern. Moreover, some schools do not follow the DepEd's standard student-teacher ratio.

According to the teachers at these schools in a follow-up interview conducted, they were forced to congest their classes due to classroom shortages, inadequate infrastructure, insufficient teaching staff, or a rapid increase in student enrollment.

d. Environment

Table 8. The Teaching and Learning Environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Resources

Resources	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The school has available books and other reference materials.	3.04	Agree	3.14	Agree
2. The school has available learner's materials in all learning areas.	2.92	Agree	3.09	Agree
3. The school has accessible instructional materials.	3.13	Agree	3.14	Agree
4. The school has available teacher's guides in all learning areas.	3.11	Agree	3.17	Agree
5. The school has available curriculum guides in all learning areas.	3.40	Strongly Agree	3.24	Agree
6. The school provides students access to ADM, ALS, and/or other learning materials for their use during emergencies.	3.28	Strongly Agree	3.09	Agree
7. Each classroom has a chalkboard or whiteboard.	3.63	Strongly Agree	3.30	Strongly Agree
8. Classrooms have adequate chairs and tables for students.	3.25	Strongly Agree	3.25	Strongly Agree
9. The school has adequate teacher's tables and chairs.	3.43	Strongly Agree	3.24	Agree
10. Classrooms have functional CIA boards.	3.39	Strongly Agree	3.28	Strongly Agree
11. All classrooms have adequate emergency/first aid kits that are readily available.	3.22	Agree	3.15	Agree

Average Weighted Mean	3.25	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree
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Table 8 presents the responses of the respondents on the teaching and learning environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as perceived by the respondents in terms of resources.

Data revealed, that the teacher respondents have better perceptions of the teaching and learning environment in terms of resources compared to the student-respondents with an average weighted mean of 3.25 for the teacher-respondents and 3.19 for the student-respondents. Teachers may have a more positive perception of the teaching and learning environment in terms of resources compared to students because they are more familiar with the overall resources and facilities within the school, as they work closely with them daily. They may have access to information about the school's resources and are more attuned to the various tools and materials at their disposal. On the other hand, students might not be as well informed about the full range of resources available in the school. Their perspective may be limited to what they directly encounter in classrooms, and they might not have a comprehensive understanding of the broader array of educational tools and facilities.

Both the teacher and student respondents have the same perceptions on items availability of books and other reference materials, availability of learner's materials in all learning areas, availability of instructional materials, availability of chalkboard or whiteboard, availability of chairs and tables for students, availability of functional CIA board and availability of emergency/first aid kits while they differ in items availability of curriculum guides in all learning areas, availability of ADM, ALS, and/or other learning materials for their use during emergencies and availability of teacher's table and chair.

The item on the availability of learner's materials in all learning areas obtained the lowest weighted mean for both teacher and student respondents with average weighted means of 2.92 and 3.09, respectively.

The cited findings are supported by the study of Combalicer (2016) where one of the most pressing problems encountered by the teachers in the initial implementation of the K to 12 curriculum is the unavailability of modules for the different subject areas, lack of textbooks in the different subject areas, and very few available reading materials for project materials and research work. This problem can have negative effects on both students and teachers, impacting their motivation and performance in the educational setting. According to Maffea (2020), the lack of resources in classrooms cannot only cause extreme distress to the students and teachers, but they are unable to learn to their fullest potential because they are not being given the proper resources.

e. Technology

Table 9. The Teaching and Learning Environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as Perceived by the Respondents in Terms of Technology

Technology	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The school has available ICT equipment.	3.45	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree
2. Classrooms have multimedia and speakers.	3.05	Agree	3.08	Agree
3. The school has an accessible internet connection.	3.01	Agree	2.82	Agree
4. All classrooms have a television/projector.	3.16	Agree	3.15	Agree
5. Each classroom has a printer and scanner.	2.65	Agree	2.85	Agree
6. The school has a photocopier.	3.29	Strongly Agree	2.95	Agree
7. The school has a sound system.	3.44	Strongly Agree	3.18	Agree
8. The school has musical instruments.	2.35	Agree	2.99	Agree
9. The school has a functional Facebook page for school updates.	3.57	Strongly Agree	3.37	Agree
10. The school has a system to regularly check on the attendance of its pupils and address problems concerning non-attendance.	3.09	Agree	3.28	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.11	Agree	3.09	Agree

Table 9 presents the teaching and learning environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as perceived by the respondents in terms of technology. The two groups of respondents rated it 'Agree' or 3.11 (teachers) and 3.09 (students) weighted means, respectively.

The data reveal that both the teacher and student respondents have the same level of perception of the teaching-learning environment of the schools in terms of technology in general. However, the items on availability of ICT equipment, availability of photocopier, availability of sound system, and availability of functional school Facebook

page have different perceptions. Teachers have a more positive perception of the said items because they may have access to information about the school's technology infrastructure, including updates, improvements, and any limitations. This insider knowledge allows them to better gauge the overall technological environment within the school.

As shown in the table the items on availability of musical instruments and accessibility of internet connection gained the lowest means. This indicates that some schools in the City Division of Ilagan offering Senior High School Program still experiencing gaps in terms of resources particularly on internet accessibility which can have repercussions on motivation and performance of students and teachers.

Wherein according to Amponsah (2022) access to the Internet improves academic standards among students, as those with Internet access showed more significant progress in their academic performance than those who did not.

Table 10. Summary of the Teaching and Learning Environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as Perceived by the Respondents

Teaching and Learning Environment	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Facilities	3.12	Agree	3.20	Agree
2. Environment	3.48	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree
3. Support	3.34	Strongly Agree	3.19	Agree
4. Resources	3.25	Strongly Agree	3.19	Strongly Agree
5. Technology	3.11	Agree	3.09	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.26	Strongly Agree	3.17	Agree

Table 10 shows the summary of the teaching and learning environment of the Senior High Schools in the City Division of Ilagan as perceived by the two groups of respondents.

The teacher respondents generally rated the teaching-learning environment of the Senior High Schools 'Strongly Agree' with a 3.26 average weighted mean while the student respondents generally rated it 'Agree' with a 3.17 average weighted mean. This signifies that teachers have a better perception of the teaching-learning environment of the Senior High School compared to the student respondents considering the average weighted means.

Teachers have a more favorable perception of the teaching and learning environment compared to students due to their unique perspectives and professional roles. Teachers are deeply involved in the planning and execution of educational

activities, giving them a firsthand understanding of the facilities, support systems, environment, resources, and technology available. They interact with these elements daily, experiencing both their strengths and limitations. Additionally, teachers are responsible for adapting their teaching methods to cater to diverse student needs, which requires a nuanced understanding of the learning environment. In contrast, students may not be as attuned to the broader institutional considerations, and their perspective is often centered on their individual experiences within the classroom. Teachers, being stakeholders in the educational process, are also more likely to be aware of changes, updates, and challenges in the system, contributing to a more informed perception of the overall teaching and learning environment.

Comparison in the Perception of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Teaching-learning Environment

Table 11. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers and Students on the Teaching–Learning Environment

Variables	Mean		Probability of t	Remarks
	Teachers	Students		
Facilities	3.12	3.20	0.0467	Significant
Environment	3.48	3.19	0.0001	Significant
Support	3.34	3.19	0.0009	Significant
Resources	3.25	3.19	0.0470	Significant
Technology	3.11	3.09	0.4000	Not Significant

Table 11 presents the results of the test of significant differences in the perception of the teachers and students in the teaching-learning environment.

The results show that the t-probability values are less than 0.05 except for technology. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the perception of the teachers and students of the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, support, and resources. It implies that the teachers' perception of the said four areas of the teaching-learning environment differs from that of the students. As indicated by the mean in the table, it further infers that the teachers have better perceptions of environment, support, and resources for they obtain the higher mean, while the students perceive better the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities since they got the higher mean.

However, there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers and students of the teaching-learning environment in terms of technology. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It states that the teachers and the students do not differ from each other in their perceptions of technology. It shows that they have similarities in their perceptions of teaching and learning environments in terms of technology. Teachers and students often share similar perceptions regarding the availability and use of technology in the school environment for various reasons. One crucial factor is the establishment of a shared experience where both teachers and

students have consistent access to modern tools and resources. When the school fosters a collaborative learning environment that encourages the integration of technology into teaching and learning practices, it can lead to a collective positive perception.

Comparison in the Perception of the Respondents of the Teaching-learning Environment Grouped by Profile

a. Teachers

1. School Size

Table 12. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Teaching-Learning Environment when Grouped According to School Size

Variables	Mean			Probability of F	Remarks
	Very Large	Large	Small		
Facilities and School Size	2.91	3.14	3.25	0.0008	Significant
Environment and School Size	3.28	3.52	3.60	0.0006	Significant
Support and School Size	3.36	3.36	3.30	0.0627	Not Significant
Resources and School Size	2.95	3.30	3.43	0.0000	Significant
Technology and School Size	3.00	3.02	3.22	0.0084	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the teaching-learning environment, when grouped according to school size, are presented in Table 12.

It is revealed from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 except for support. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the perception of the teachers of the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, resources, and technology when grouped according to school size. It shows that the teachers from very large schools differ in their perceptions of the aforementioned areas from those who come from large and small schools. As evidenced by the mean in the table the teachers who belong to small schools have better perceptions of the teaching-learning environment on facilities, environment, resources, and technology for they obtain the higher mean.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers of the teaching-learning environment in terms of support when grouped according to school size. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance

level. It implies that the teachers have similarities in their perceptions of support as one category of the teaching-learning environment regardless of the school size they belong.

This finding is supported by DO No. 31, s. 2016 – Implementing Guidelines on the Release and Utilization of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) Allocations of Senior High Schools which states that the MOOE budget for every year depends upon the number of enrollees. MOOE is the allocated funds for public elementary and secondary schools that can be spent on activities and necessities that support the learning programs and help maintain a safe and healthy environment in schools.

2. School Classification

Table 13. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Teaching Learning Environment when grouped according to School Classification

Variables	Mean		Probability of F	Remarks
	National	Integrated		
Facilities and School Classification	3.07	3.19	0.0310	Significant
Environment and School Classification	3.38	3.58	0.0206	Significant
Support and School Classification	3.37	3.31	0.0177	Significant
Resources and School Classification	3.17	3.37	0.0009	Significant
Technology and School Classification	3.09	3.12	0.0526	Not Significant

Table 13 displays the results of the test of significant differences in the perception of the teachers on the teaching-learning environment when grouped according to school classification.

The results reflect that the F-probability values are less than 0.05 except for technology. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant difference in the perception of teachers on the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, support, and resources when grouped according to school classification. It shows that the perception of the teachers who belong to integrated schools differs from those who come from national schools. It further notes as indicated by the mean in the table that the teachers who teach in integrated schools have a better perception of facilities, facilities, environment, and resources for they obtain the higher means. While the teachers of national schools perceive better support since they have the higher mean.

However, there is no significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the teaching-learning environment in terms of technology when grouped according to school

classification. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It implies that both teachers of national and integrated schools have similarities in their perceptions of technology as one indicator of the teaching-learning environment.

Many schools in the Philippines, regardless of their classification, may face similar challenges when it comes to resources, including technological resources. Issues such as limited access to computers, internet connectivity, and relevant software can be prevalent in both national and integrated schools. This could be one of the reasons why teachers perceived similarly the teaching-learning environment in terms of technology regardless of their school classification. In a report released by the Philippine Star in 2023, the Philippines was among the countries reported to have insufficient computers in schools, leading to more disadvantaged students, especially in rural areas. Moreover, the lack of devices and digital infrastructure also makes it difficult for teachers to integrate technology into their professional tasks, according to the report.

3. School Location

Table 14. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Teachers on the Teaching Learning Environment when grouped according to School Location

Variables	Mean		Probability of F	Remarks
	Urban	Rural		
Facilities and School Location	3.00	3.26	0.0006	Significant
Environment and School Location	3.37	3.60	0.0010	Significant
Support and School Location	3.36	3.32	0.0178	Significant
Resources and School Location	3.10	3.43	0.0000	Significant
Technology and School Location	3.01	3.21	0.0260	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the teaching-learning environment when grouped according to school location are displayed in Table 14. It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the perception of the teachers on the teaching-learning when grouped according to school location. It shows that the perception of teachers from urban schools differs from those who are from rural schools. This is evidenced by the mean in the table that the teachers whose schools are mean in the table that the teachers whose schools are located in rural areas have better perceptions of the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, resources, and technology for they obtain the higher mean. Whereas the teachers from urban schools have a better perception of support since they got the higher mean. This contradicts the study by Hassan (2018) in which he stated that in urban schools all types of facilities are mostly available like

electricity, furniture, well-equipped classrooms, water, toilets, and teaching staff. But in rural areas these facilities are not available; electricity and furniture are not available.

b. Students

1. School Size

Table 15. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Students on the Teaching-Learning Environment when grouped according to School Size.

Variables	Mean			Probability of F	Remarks
	Very Large	Large	Small		
Facilities and School Size	3.13	3.25	3.26	0.0111	Significant
Environment and School Size	3.15	3.09	3.30	0.0002	Significant
Support and School Size	3.20	3.20	3.17	0.8318	Not Significant
Resources and School Size	3.15	3.17	3.25	0.0094	Significant
Technology and School Size	3.05	3.12	3.12	0.3268	Not Significant

Table 15 discloses the results of the test of significant differences in the perception of the students on the teaching-learning environment when grouped according to school size.

The results reveal that the F- probability values are less than 0.05 except for support and technology. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the perception of the students of the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, and resources when grouped according to school size. It shows that the students differ from each other in their perceptions of the aforementioned three areas of the teaching-learning environment when classified by school size. As indicated by the mean in the table, the students who belong to small schools have better perceptions of the said three areas for they have the higher mean. Teachers and students in small schools may have better perceptions of the teaching and learning environment since small schools often have smaller class sizes, which allow for more individualized attention from teachers. This can lead to a more supportive and personalized learning experience for students.

According to Blatchford et al. (2009), teachers in small classes are more likely to give individual attention to students, effectively control and manage the classroom, and build better relationships with students. Similarly, students in small classes may be more engaged in the classroom and more likely to interact with teachers and peers.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the students on the teaching-learning environment in terms of support and technology when

grouped according to school size. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It implies that the students have similarities in their perceptions of support and technology regardless of their school size. One of the reasons that support this finding is the allocation of MOOE for public schools. MOOE or Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses, is a budgetary allocation provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) in many countries to support the day-to-day operations of schools. It includes funds for various needs such as utilities, supplies, and other operational expenses. The allocation of MOOE is uniform across schools of different sizes. This ensures that regardless of the school's size, there is an equitable distribution of funds for essential resources, materials, and support services based on the guidelines set as per DepEd Order No. 31, s, 2016.

2. School Classification

Table 16. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Students on the Teaching-Learning Environment when Grouped according to School Classification

Variables	Mean		Probability of F	Remarks
	National	Integrated		
Facilities and School Classification	3.16	3.26	0.0122	Significant
Environment and School Classification	3.19	3.20	0.4888	Not Significant
Support and School Classification	3.18	3.20	0.3846	Not Significant
Resources and School Classification	3.17	3.23	0.0340	Significant
Technology and School Classification	3.07	3.11	0.0382	Significant

The results of the test of significant differences in the perception of the students on the teaching-learning environment when grouped according to school classification are disclosed in Table 16.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 except for environment and support. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a five percent significance level. As a result, there is a significant difference in the perception of the students of the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, resources, and technology. It states that students from integrated schools differ in their perceptions of the aforesaid areas of the teaching-learning environment from those students at national schools. It is further inferred, as indicated by the mean in the table, that the students from the integrated schools have better perceptions of facilities, resources, and technology for they obtain the higher mean.

However, there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the students on the teaching-learning environment in terms of environment and support when grouped according to school classification. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at five percent significance level. It implies that the students have similarities on their perceptions of the teaching-learning environment along the said two areas regardless of their school classification.

3. School Location

Table 17. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Perception of the Students on the Teaching-Learning Environment when Grouped according to School Location

Variables	Mean		Probability of F	Remarks
	Urban	Rural		
Facilities and School Location	3.17	3.36	0.0500	Significant
Environment and School Location	3.13	3.30	0.0080	Significant
Support and School Location	3.20	3.17	0.0862	Not Significant
Resources and School Location	3.15	3.25	0.0276	Significant
Technology and School Location	3.07	3.12	0.0221	Significant

Table 17 exhibits the results of the test of significant differences in the perception of the students on the teaching-learning environment when grouped according to school location.

The results reflect that the F- probability values are less than 0.05 except for support. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a five percent level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the perception of the students of the teaching-learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, resources, and technology when grouped according to school location. It shows that the students perceive differently the teaching-learning environment in the aforesaid four areas when clustered by school location. As evidenced by the mean in the table, the students who are from rural schools have better perceptions of the teaching-learning environment along with facilities, environment, resources, and technology for they got the higher mean.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the students on the teaching-learning environment in terms of support when grouped according to school classification. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It states that the students have similarities in their perceptions of support as one of the areas of the teaching-learning environment regardless of their school classification. This is because the schools receive equal support from the DepEd through MOOE which provides the financial resources necessary for the effective and efficient operation of educational institutions.

The Level of Teaching and Learning Motivation of Teachers and Students

a. Intrinsic

Table 18. The Level of Teaching and Learning Motivation of Teachers and students in terms of Intrinsic

Intrinsic	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
I feel excited going to school every day.	3.39	Highly Motivated	3.25	Highly Motivated
I enjoy the atmosphere in my classroom.	3.39	Highly Motivated	3.12	Motivated
I feel at home in my school. It is my second home.	3.43	Highly Motivated	3.26	Highly Motivated
I feel safe and comfortable in the school.	3.43	Highly Motivated	3.23	Motivated
I feel confident when I am at school.	3.47	Highly Motivated	3.09	Motivated
I am satisfied with the culture of the school.	3.23	Motivated	3.20	Motivated
My school embarks good values necessary for life.	3.40	Highly Motivated	3.36	Highly Motivated
The school where I work/learn contributes to my recognition.	3.42	Highly Motivated	3.32	Highly Motivated
I feel motivated to do my schoolwork.	3.33	Highly Motivated	3.18	Motivated
I perform my best in my daily work/task.	3.50	Highly Motivated	3.21	Motivated
I can use my creativity in the school where I work/study.	3.47	Highly Motivated	3.30	Highly Motivated
My potentials are fully utilized in this school.	3.40	Highly Motivated	3.17	Motivated
I am satisfied with my performance in school.	3.46	Highly Motivated	3.21	Motivated
I have authority to take decisions about my teaching/learning.	3.56	Highly Motivated	3.27	Highly Motivated
I am motivated to assist the school in meeting its objectives/vision and mission.	3.46	Highly Motivated	3.17	Motivated

I am adequately treated/ respected by my teachers/school head.	3.54	Highly Motivated	3.36	Highly Motivated
I have a good relationship with my colleagues, students, and their parents.	3.58	Highly Motivated	3.34	Highly Motivated
My colleagues inspire me, they are the best people to work with.	3.40	Highly Motivated	3.23	Motivated
I appreciate the management/teaching style of my school head/teachers.	3.31	Highly Motivated	3.40	Highly Motivated
My school head/teachers listen to my concerns and support reasonable suggestions.	3.43	Highly Motivated	3.31	Highly Motivated
My school head/teacher clearly communicate job performance expectations.	3.34	Highly Motivated	3.36	Highly Motivated
My school head/teacher has a professional judgement and is fair in his/her rating/grade to me.	3.45	Highly Motivated	3.12	Motivated
I am encouraged by my school head/teachers to perform well.	3.51	Highly Motivated	3.33	Highly Motivated
Average Weighted Mean	3.43	Highly Motivated	3.25	Highly Motivated

Table 18 presents the level of teaching and learning motivation of teachers and students in terms of Intrinsic.

The data reveal that both teacher and student respondents have the same level of teaching and learning motivation in terms of intrinsic. They rated it as “Highly Motivated” with a 3.43 average weighted mean for teacher- respondents and 3.25 for student-respondents. However, on some items such as “I enjoy the atmosphere in my classroom”, “I feel safe and comfortable in the school”, “I feel confident when I am at school”, “I feel motivated to do my schoolwork”, “I perform my best in my daily work/task”, “My potentials are fully utilized in this school”, “I am satisfied with my performance in school”, “I am motivated to assist the school in meeting its objectives/vision and mission”, “My

colleagues inspire me, they are the best people to work with”, and “My school head/teacher has a professional judgment and is fair in his/her rating/grade to me” the teacher- respondents displayed a higher level of motivation compared to the student-respondents.

A combination of factors, including a positive learning environment, supportive relationships, recognition of achievements, rewards, clear goals, and growth opportunities, contributes to the high motivation levels observed among both learners and teachers. Schools in the City Division of Ilagan often implement recognition programs to honor outstanding teachers, administrators, and staff members who demonstrate excellence in their roles. This may involve awards ceremonies, certificates of appreciation, or public acknowledgment of their achievements. Similarly, students were also given recognition for their achievements and accomplishments. Thus, by fostering these conditions, schools can create environments where motivation thrives, leading to improved outcomes for both teachers and students.

b. Extrinsic

Table 19. The Level of Teaching and Learning Motivation of Teachers and students in terms of Extrinsic

Extrinsic	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
I am motivated by the salary, benefits, and allowances I am receiving.	3.23	Motivated		Motivated
I am motivated by the benefits I am receiving in this school.			3.22	
Promotions are properly implemented.	2.96	Motivated		Motivated
The school has a dropout reduction program, 100 percent grade level promotion.			3.05	
I receive sufficient and appropriate performance recognition.	3.32	Highly Motivated	3.20	Motivated
The school provides me opportunities to actively participate in school decisions.	3.27	Highly Motivated	3.25	Highly Motivated
The school provides me opportunities for learning/professional development.	3.34	Highly Motivated	3.30	Highly Motivated

I have appropriate equipment to perform my duties/task effectively.	3.25	Highly Motivated	3.13	Motivated
I have access to teaching/learning materials and resources in my school.	3.38	Highly Motivated	3.16	Motivated
The facilities in my school boost my morale.	3.21	Motivated	3.11	Motivated
WASH facilities provide me comfortable teaching-learning environment.	3.35	Highly Motivated	3.21	Motivated
ICT equipment makes teaching-learning process more fun and interesting.	3.40	Highly Motivated	3.16	Motivated
Well-equipped classrooms provide me favorable settings for teaching/learning.	3.41	Highly Motivated	3.18	Motivated
Laboratory enhances my effectiveness in teaching/learning	3.25	Highly Motivated	3.05	Motivated
School library equipped with books enhance my effectiveness in teaching/learning	2.95	Motivated	3.11	Motivated
Recreational and sporting facilities enhance my effectiveness in teaching/learning	2.98	Motivated	3.10	Motivated
Instructional facilities help me in the effective and efficient delivery of the lesson.	3.32	Highly Motivated		Motivated
Instructional facilities help me to learn effectively and efficiently.			3.21	
Average Weighted Mean	3.24	Motivated	3.16	Motivated

Table 19 provides data on the level of teaching and learning motivation of teachers and students in terms of Extrinsic.

The table shows that both teacher and student respondents have the same level of teaching and learning motivation in terms of extrinsic. They rated it as “Motivated” with

a 3.24 average weighted mean for teacher- respondents and 3.16 for student-respondents. However, items including “I receive sufficient and appropriate performance recognition”, “I have the appropriate equipment to perform my duties/task effectively”, “I have access to teaching materials and resources in my school”, and “WASH facilities provide me comfortable teaching-learning environment”, “ICT equipment makes the teaching-learning process more fun and interesting”, “Well-equipped classrooms provide me favorable settings for teaching/learning”, “Laboratory enhances my effectiveness in teaching/learning”, and “Instructional facilities help me in the effective and efficient delivery of the lesson/ Instructional facilities help me to learn effectively and efficiently” the teacher- respondents got higher weighted means. This means that they have a higher level of extrinsic motivation on the said items compared to the student- respondents.

The item “Promotions are properly implemented” obtained the lowest mean for teachers, while the item “Laboratory enhances my learning” got the lowest mean for the students. The results suggest that teachers are not fully motivated in terms of promotion implementation, and some students are not fully motivated because of the insufficient laboratory facilities in their schools.

Table 20. Summary of the Level of Teaching and Learning Motivation of Teachers and Students

Motivation	Teachers		Students	
	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Intrinsic	3.43	Highly Motivated	3.25	Highly Motivated
2. Extrinsic	3.24	Motivated	3.16	Motivated
Average Weighted Mean	3.34	Highly Motivated	3.21	Motivated

Table 20 shows the summary of the level of teaching and learning motivation of the respondents.

As shown in the table, both the teacher and student respondents have high levels of intrinsic teaching-learning motivation with a 3.43 weighted mean for teachers and 3.25 for students. In terms of extrinsic motivation, the two groups of respondents rated “Motivated” with a weighted mean of 3.24 for teachers and 3.16 for students. This means that teacher and student respondents have higher levels of intrinsic teaching and learning motivation compared to extrinsic.

Access to appropriate resources and well-maintained facilities can enhance the overall teaching-learning experience and contribute to a positive and motivating environment. However, some teachers and students feel that they lack access to these essential resources and facilities of the school which may lead to decreased motivation among them. In an interview conducted, some of the student- respondents said that their school lacked learning materials, textbooks, technology, or other resources, and had inadequate or poorly maintained facilities, such as laboratories, classrooms, and libraries.

According to a report by the Department of Education, many schools lack adequate classrooms, textbooks, and teaching materials, making it challenging for students to learn effectively. This challenge is not only limited to rural areas but is also present in urban areas. The absence of these tools and materials needed for effective learning could be the reason why they are less motivated.

Comparison between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Levels of Motivation as Perceived by the Two Groups of Respondents

Table 21. Results of the Test of Significant Differences in the Level of Motivation as Perceived by the Teachers and Students in Terms of Intrinsic and Extrinsic

Level of Motivation	Mean		Probability of t	Remarks
	Teachers	Students		
Intrinsic	3.43	3.25	0.0007	Significant
Extrinsic	3.24	3.16	0.0425	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of motivation as perceived by the teachers and students in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic are exhibited in Table 21.

It is evident from the results that the probability t-values are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection the rejection of the null hypothesis at five percent level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of motivation as perceived by the teachers and the students in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic. It shows that the teachers' perception of the level of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation differs from that of the students. As indicated by the mean in the table, the teachers have better perceptions of their intrinsic and extrinsic level of motivation for they obtain the higher mean.

The disparity in the perceived intrinsic and extrinsic motivation between teachers and students can be attributed to factors such as professional development, autonomy, varied roles, and life experience. Teachers, through their extensive training and diverse roles, often gain a deeper understanding of their motivation levels compared to students who may be navigating a more structured and externally guided educational journey. Recognizing these differences is essential for fostering effective communication and collaboration between educators and students, ultimately enhancing the learning experience for all parties involved.

Comparison in the Level of Motivation of the Respondents when Grouped by Profile

a. Teachers

1. Intrinsic

Table 22. Results of the Test of Significant Differences in the Level of Motivation of the Teachers in terms of Intrinsic when Grouped by School Profile

Variables	Mean			Probability of F	Remarks
	Very Large	Large	Small		
Intrinsic and School Size	3.29	3.37	3.55	0.0009	Significant
Intrinsic and School Classification	National		Integrated	0.0309	Significant
	3.36		3.50		
Intrinsic and School Location	Urban		Rural	0.0007	Significant
	3.32		3.55		

Table 22 presents the results of significant differences in the level of motivation of the teachers in terms of intrinsic when grouped according to school profile.

The results show that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. As a result, there is a significant difference in the level of motivation of teachers in terms of intrinsic when grouped according to school profile. It indicates that the teachers vary in their level of intrinsic motivation when clustered by school size, school classification, and school location. As evidenced by the mean in the table, the teachers, who belong to small, integrated, and rural schools have better levels of intrinsic motivation for they obtain the higher mean.

The higher level of intrinsic motivation observed among teachers in small, integrated, and rural schools can be attributed to a combination of factors, including a strong sense of community, personalized relationships, autonomy, perceived impact, professional collaboration, reduced bureaucracy, and alignment of values. Thus, understanding these contributing factors provides valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders aiming to enhance teacher motivation and, consequently, the overall quality of the teaching-learning environment. Ultimately, fostering a supportive and empowering professional culture is crucial for nurturing the intrinsic motivation that drives educators to excel in their noble pursuit of shaping young minds.

2. Extrinsic

Table 23. Results of the Test of Significant Differences in the Level of Motivation of the Teachers in terms of Extrinsic when Grouped by School Profile

Variables	Mean			Probability of F	Remarks
	Very Large	Large	Small		
Extrinsic and School Size	3.16	2.96	3.42	0.0005	Significant
Extrinsic and School Classification	National		Integrated	0.0582	Not Significant
	3.25		3.23		
Extrinsic and School Location	Urban		Rural	0.0000	Significant
	3.08		3.42		

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of motivation of the teachers in terms of extrinsic, when grouped according to school profile, are presented in Table 23.

It is posted in the table that the F-probability values are less than 0.05 except for school classification. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the level of motivation of the teachers in terms of extrinsic when grouped according to school size and location. It shows that the teachers differ from each other in their level of extrinsic motivation when grouped by the said school profiles. As evidenced by the mean in the table, it notes further that the teachers who are from small and rural schools have better levels of extrinsic motivation for they obtain the higher mean.

This contradicts the study of Takupiwa (2013) that teachers in rural areas are more poorly motivated and dissatisfied than their urban counterparts with their living and working conditions. Low wages when compared with urban teachers, lack of promotion opportunities, lack of career advancement opportunities, high teacher-pupil ratio, poor work environment, and inadequate fringe benefits contributed to lower teachers' morale in rural areas.

However, there is no significant difference in the level of motivation of teachers in terms of extrinsic when grouped according to school classification. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It implies that the teachers have similarities in their level of extrinsic motivation regardless of their school classification.

b. Students

1. Intrinsic

Table 24. Results of the Test of Significant Differences in the Level of Motivation of the Students in terms of Intrinsic when Grouped by School Profile

Variables	Mean			Probability of F	Remarks
	Very Large	Large	Small		
Intrinsic and School Size	3.20	3.22	3.35	0.0097	Significant
Intrinsic and School Classification	National		Integrated	0.0157	Significant
	3.23		3.29		
Intrinsic and School Location	Urban		Rural	0.0095	Significant
	3.21		3.35		

Table 24 displays the results of significant differences in the level of motivation of the students in terms of intrinsic when grouped according to school profile.

The results reveal that the F-probability values are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of motivation of the students in terms of intrinsic when grouped according to school profile. It states that the students have varied levels of intrinsic motivation when they are clustered by school size, classification, and location. It is further inferred as indicated by the mean in the table, that the students who belong to small, integrated, and rural schools have better levels of intrinsic motivation for they got the higher mean. It was supported by the findings of Grauer (2019) which indicate that students from small schools are more engaged, connected, and intrinsically motivated than students who attend larger schools.

b. Students

2. Extrinsic

Table 25. Results of the Test of Significant Differences in the Level of Motivation of the Students in terms of Extrinsic when Grouped by School Profile

Variables	Mean			Probability of F	Remarks
	Very Large	Large	Small		
Extrinsic and School Size	3.16	3.08	3.35	0.0096	Significant
Extrinsic and School Classification	National		Integrated	0.2560	Not Significant
	3.17		3.15		
	Urban		Rural	0.0004	Significant

Extrinsic and School Location	3.14	3.21		
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The results of the test of significant difference in the level of motivation of the students in terms of extrinsic, when grouped according to school profile, are displayed in Table 25.

It is reflected from the results that the probability values of F are less than a five percent significance level except for school classification. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. As a result, there is a significant difference in the level of motivation of students in terms of extrinsic when grouped according to school size and location. It states that the students have different levels of extrinsic motivation when they are classified by the said two school profiles. As evidenced by the mean in the table, the students from small and rural schools have better levels of extrinsic motivation for they obtain the higher mean.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the level of motivation of the students in terms of extrinsic when grouped according to school classification. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It implies that the students have similarities in their level of extrinsic motivation regardless of their school classification.

Performance of the Students and Teachers

Table 26. Performance of Teachers

Rating	Qualitative Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	177	84.69
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	32	15.31
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	0	0
1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory	0	0
below 1.499	Poor	0	0
Total		209	100

Table 26 presents the data on the performance of teachers in public Senior High Schools in the City Division for the school year 2022- 2023.

The results show that 177 or 84.69 percent had 4.500- 5000 or Outstanding performance and 32 or 15. 31 percent has 3.500- 4.499 or Very Satisfactory performance. This implies that most of the teacher respondents have outstanding performance based on the guidelines and criteria set as per DepEd Order No. 2, s. of 2015, titled Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS).

Outstanding performance often stems from a combination of factors, including personal dedication, support from the education system, and a conducive work environment. When these elements align, teachers can thrive and make a significant impact on their students' learning experiences. According to Surya (2004) several factors affect the performance of teachers including reward, safety, interpersonal relationships, working environment conditions, and opportunities for self-development and improvement. Hence if the teachers were provided professional development opportunities, mentoring programs, and classroom resources, they are more likely to excel in their roles. In the Department of Education, teachers were provided adequate trainings to ensure that the learners receive the best education possible. Furthermore, it was also found out that the schools in the City Division offering Senior High School have favorable teaching and learning environment which is also one of the several factors that affect the performance of the teachers. These could be the reasons why the SHS teachers in the City Division of Ilagan have outstanding performance.

Table 27. Performance of Students

Rating	Qualitative Description	Frequency	Percentage
90-100	Outstanding	210	56.45
85-89	Very Satisfactory	118	31.72
80-84	Satisfactory	28	7.53
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	16	4.30
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectation	0	0
Total		372	100

Table 27 displays the performance of the student respondents for the school year 2022- 2023.

Among the 372 respondents, 210 or 56. 45 percent had 90- 100 or Outstanding performance, 118 or 31.72 percent had 85-89 or Very Satisfactory performance, 28 or 7.53 percent had 80- 84 or Satisfactory performance, and 16 or 4.30 percent had 75- 79 or Fairly Satisfactory performance. This signifies that the majority of respondents have outstanding performance based on the criteria set as per DepEd Order No. 8, s. of 2015, titled Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program.

Comparison in the Perceived Teaching and Learning Environment, Level of Motivation, and Performance of the Respondents

a. Teachers

1. Intrinsic Motivation

Table 28. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Perceived Teaching and Learning Environment and the Level of Intrinsic Motivation of the Teachers

Variables	Probability of r	Remarks
Facilities and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0005	Significant
Environment and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0003	Significant
Support and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0007	Significant
Resources and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0001	Significant
Technology and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0009	Significant

Table 28 discloses the results of the test of a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of intrinsic motivation of the teacher.

The results show that the probability values of r are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a five percent level of significance. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of intrinsic motivation of the teachers. It implies that the teachers' perception of the teaching and learning environment in terms of facilities, environment support, resources, and technology significantly affects the intrinsic motivation of the teachers.

Teachers' perception of the teaching and learning environment indeed plays a pivotal role in shaping their intrinsic motivation. When teachers perceive a positive and well-equipped environment, it fosters a sense of efficacy and purpose. Adequate facilities and resources enhance their ability to deliver quality education, while a supportive atmosphere encourages collaboration and professional growth. Technology integration provides tools to innovate teaching methods, making lessons more engaging. Conversely, if teachers perceive deficiencies or lack of support in these areas, it can lead to frustration and demotivation. In essence, a conducive teaching and learning environment empowers teachers, boosting their intrinsic motivation and, consequently, positively impacting the quality of education they provide. Thus, it is stated in the DepEd Educational Facilities Manual that improving school facilities is crucial for creating a positive and effective learning environment, thus, increasing motivation and better performance.

2. Extrinsic Motivation

Table 29. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Perceived Teaching and Learning Environment and the Level of Extrinsic Motivation of the Teachers

Variables	Probability of r	Remarks
Facilities and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0007	Significant
Environment and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0004	Significant
Support and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0009	Significant
Resources and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0005	Significant
Technology and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0008	Significant

The results of the test of a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of extrinsic motivation of the teachers are disclosed in Table 29.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of r are less than 0.005. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a five percent significance level. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of extrinsic motivation of the teachers. It shows that the teachers' extrinsic motivation is significantly affected by their perceived teaching and learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, support, resources, and technology. Thus, schools should prioritize creating a conducive atmosphere where teachers feel valued, supported, and equipped to excel in their roles, ultimately enhancing their overall motivation to contribute meaningfully to the learning experiences of their students.

3. Performance

Table 30. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Perceived Teaching and Learning Environment and the Level of Motivation to the Performance of the Teachers.

Variables	Probability of X ²	Remarks
Facilities and Performance	0.1563	Not Significant
Environment and Performance	0.1877	Not Significant
Support and Performance	0.1905	Not Significant
Resources and Performance	0.2658	Not Significant
Technology and Performance	0.1894	Not Significant
Intrinsic Motivation and Performance	0.1560	Not Significant
Extrinsic Motivation and Performance	0.0090	Significant

Table 30 exhibits the results of the test of the significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of motivation to the performance of the teachers.

The results reveal that the probability values of Chi-square (X^2) are greater than 0.05 except for extrinsic motivation and performance. For this reason, the null hypothesis is accepted at a five percent level of significance. As a result, there is no significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of intrinsic motivation for the performance of the teachers. It implies that the teachers' perception of the teaching and learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, support, resources, and technology had no significant effect on their performance. Likewise, the intrinsic motivation of the teachers does not significantly affect their performance. The cited findings opposed the findings of Abbas et. al (2022) and Octaviani, et.al (2022) that the school's environment influences the performance of teachers.

However, there is a significant relationship between the level of extrinsic motivation of the teachers and their performance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. It states that the teachers' performance is significantly affected by their extrinsic motivation. The results are relevant to the previous study conducted by Kumari & Kumar (2023) discovered that non-self-determined motivation has a significant relationship with teachers' job performance. It presents that once teachers are externally motivated in terms of job security, rewards and compensation for their performance become high. The findings of this study also complement the findings of Khwaja et al. (2018) that all external factors positively and significantly influence teacher performance. Hence, it is evident that any form of performance is an outcome of encouragement received from the organization, which eventually improves their performance and increases productivity.

b. Students

1. Intrinsic Motivation

Table 31. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Perceived Teaching and Learning Environment and the Level of Intrinsic Motivation of the Students

Variables	Probability of r	Remarks
Facilities and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0004	Significant
Environment and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0001	Significant
Support and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0003	Significant
Resources and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0006	Significant
Technology and Intrinsic Motivation	0.0007	Significant

The results of the test of a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of intrinsic motivation of the students are exhibited in Table 31.

It is evident from the results that the r-probability values are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of

intrinsic motivation of the students. It shows that the students' perception of the teaching and learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, support, resources, and technology had a significant effect on their intrinsic motivation. The study of Hafizoglu et. al (2019) on The Role of Students' Motivation in the Relationship between Perceived Learning Environment and Achievement in Science supports the present study. The results of their study showed that students who perceive their learning environment positively also have a generally high level of motivation.

Similarly, Radovan et. al (2015) also found out that students who perceive their learning environment as a place that fosters autonomy and self-direction and find their education to be useful and relevant are more intrinsically motivated.

2. Extrinsic Motivation

Table 32. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Perceived Teaching and Learning Environment and the Level of Extrinsic Motivation of the Students

Variables	Probability of r	Remarks
Facilities and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0009	Significant
Environment and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0005	Significant
Support and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0002	Significant
Resources and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0006	Significant
Technology and Extrinsic Motivation	0.0007	Significant

Table 32 displays the results of the test of a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of extrinsic motivation of the students.

The results reveal that the probability values of r are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of extrinsic motivation of students. It shows that the students' perception of the teaching and learning environment in terms of facilities, environment, support, resources, and technology significantly affects their extrinsic motivation. This finding is supported by the study of Acomolafe and Adesua (2016) and Abellanosa (2019) which showed that there is a significant relationship between physical facilities and students' level of motivation.

3. Performance

Table 33. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Perceived Teaching and Learning Environment and the Level of Motivation to the Performance of the Students

Variables	Probability of x^2	Remarks
Facilities and Performance	0.9464	Not Significant
Environment and Performance	0.0068	Significant

Support and Performance	0.0042	Significant
Resources and Performance	0.0852	Not Significant
Technology and Performance	0.0431	Significant
Intrinsic Motivation and Performance	0.0439	Significant
Extrinsic Motivation and Performance	0.0455	Significant

The results of the test of the significant relationship of the perceived teaching and learning environment and the level of motivation to the performance of the students are disclosed in Table 33.

It is reflected from the results that the Chi-square (X^2) probability values are less than 0.05 except for facilities and resources. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. As a result, there is a significant relationship between the perceived teaching and learning environment in terms of environment, support, and technology and the level of motivation of the students to the performance of the students. It implies that the teaching and learning environment along the mentioned three areas and the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation have significant effects on the performance of the students. The cited findings are supported by the study of Usman et. al (2019), Havidz, & Mujakiah (2023), Nyoni, et. al (2017), and Acomolafe and Adesua (2016) in which they averred that the learning environment affected the student's motivation, the learning environment affected the student achievement or performance and students' motivation affected student achievement. Thus, the teaching and learning environment plays a crucial role in shaping the motivation and performance of students. Positive, supportive, and well-organized environments tend to increase motivation and foster better learning outcomes.

However, there is no significant relationship between the teaching and learning environment in terms of facilities and resources and the performance of the students. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It states that these two areas of the teaching and learning environment have no significant effect on the performance of the students. This finding contradicted the study of Ahmed et. al (2020) that the availability and use of physical and instructional classroom environmental facilities prove helpful indicators for improving students' learning outcomes at the secondary level. It was also supported by the study of Duruji et. al (2014), Nambuya (2013), and Nyoni, et. al (2017) in which they stated that adequate learning facilities and resources significantly influence students' academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the above findings, the study concludes that the teaching and learning environment in the City Division of Ilagan was perceived by the student and teacher respondents positively with slight differences in their perception across various factors such as facilities, environment, support, resources, and technology. Teachers tend to have better perceptions of the environment, support, and resources, while students perceive facilities more positively.

In terms of their level of motivation, both groups of respondents exhibit a high level of intrinsic motivation, indicating a genuine passion for teaching and learning, with average levels of extrinsic motivation. However, there are differences in their motivation levels based on school profiles such as school size, school classification, and school location.

Regarding performance, the majority of the respondents have demonstrated outstanding performance. In terms of the relationship between the perceived teaching-learning environment, motivation levels, and performance of teachers and students, the two groups of respondents exhibit significant differences. For teachers, only extrinsic motivation demonstrated a significant effect on their performance while intrinsic motivation does not appear to have a significant impact which is contrary to several literature and studies suggesting that the teaching and learning environment and intrinsic motivation are influencing the teachers' performance. This suggests that the performance of teachers may be influenced by additional factors beyond the ones considered in the study. Conversely, for students, both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation significantly influence performance, with certain aspects of the teaching-learning environment having varying effects on motivation and performance.

Overall, the findings suggest that the teaching-learning environment, motivation levels, and performance are interconnected but can be influenced by various factors such as school size, school classification, and school location. Understanding these dynamics can help in fostering a more supportive and effective learning environment for both teachers and students.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the researcher therefore recommends the following to enhance the motivation and performance of the students and teachers:

1. A feedback mechanism relative to the effect of the teaching-learning environment on the motivation and performance of SHS teachers and students in the City Division of Ilagan be made functional by the educational authorities or administrators responsible for overseeing the City Division of Ilagan's Senior High School (SHS) system.

2. School heads should allot a considerable percentage of their Maintenance and other Operating Expenses (MOOE) for the procurement of sports equipment, TVL and Non- TVL tools and equipment, musical instruments, and for the reproduction of downloaded materials in the LRMS portal.

3. School administrators must ensure that the school library is equipped with the latest technology and adequately staffed with a designated librarian to manage its operations effectively.

4. Since it was found out that there is an unavailability of learner's material in the Senior High School in the City Division of Ilagan, it is recommended that the Learning

Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) be effectively utilized. Senior High School teachers should be encouraged and guided to utilize the LRMDS platform for downloading required instructional materials and other references necessary for senior high school education to ensure access to a comprehensive repository of educational resources, thereby enhancing the quality of teaching and learning experiences in the SHS in the City Division of Ilagan.

5. Educational administrators should evaluate the teaching-learning environment of the schools in the City Division of Ilagan and communicate the result to the stakeholders to encourage support from them.

6. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the school' teaching-learning environment in the City Division of Ilagan should be carried out to address the gaps and improve the learning situation and environment.

7. Since it was found out that there is inadequacy of non-teaching staff particularly librarian and guidance counselor in the schools in the City Division of Ilagan, Division Planning officer and Human Resource Management Officer should provide the needed non- teaching staff in schools.

8. School administrators should provide sports facilities with the required equipment, musical instruments, accessible internet connectivity, and gender-sensitive comfort rooms in schools.

9. Schools in the City Division of Ilagan should establish a quality assurance team for the provision of school facilities and to prevent any shortcomings.

10. Schools in the City Division of Ilagan should implement the 5S Principle (Sort, Set in Order, Shine, Standardize, and Sustain) to create a more organized, efficient, and secure teaching and learning environment.

11. Educational administrators should prioritize allocating resources and designing programs aimed at enhancing the skills and knowledge of teachers to ensure that they remain effective, motivated, and equipped to meet the evolving needs of students in the modern educational landscape.

12. School administrators should establish recognition programs that celebrate teachers who demonstrate exceptional dedication, innovation, and effectiveness in their roles.

13. School administrators in the City of Ilagan should prioritize addressing the identified challenges to create a conducive learning environment, as research has shown that such environments have a positive effect on students' motivation and performance. School administrators should collaborate with teachers, staff, students, parents, and other stakeholders to identify and address barriers to learning.

14. A follow- up study and other studies related to this present work be undertaken by future researchers putting greater emphasis on gaps and missing links found in the present study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms her steadfast commitment to upholding ethical research standards throughout the entirety of this study. Informed consent was meticulously obtained from all participants, emphasizing transparency, and honoring their autonomy. Participants were reassured of their right to withdraw from the study at any juncture, and stringent measures were implemented to safeguard their anonymity, preserving confidentiality throughout the research process. Furthermore, protocols were established to prioritize the well-being of participants, ensuring their safety and comfort remained paramount. The researcher maintained an unwavering dedication to integrity, diligently avoiding plagiarism and interpreting findings impartially to mitigate bias. It is underscored that the results obtained are solely intended to contribute to the advancement of knowledge, executed with the utmost adherence to ethical principles for the betterment of research and society as a whole.

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